

Funded by
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HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05

*Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460

Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D2.5

Maps of landscape impact metrics (a)

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number	D2.5
Deliverable title	Maps of landscape impact metrics (a)
Work Package	WP2
Deliverable type	DATA
Dissemination level	PU
Due date	31.12.2023 (Month 12)
Pages	29
Document version	4.0
Lead author(s)	Ruihong Chen, ETH Zurich
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The WIMBY project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. The funding in Switzerland comes from the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under the grant number 22.00449. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DOCUMENT CHANGE HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
DRAFT			
0.1	23.11.2023	Ruihong Chen, ETH Zurich	Creation
0.2	01.12.2023	Ruihong Chen, ETH Zurich	Consolidation of input from contributors
0.3	05.12.2023	Ruihong Chen, ETH Zurich	Consolidation of input from contributors
FIRST PEER REVIEW			
1.0	11.12.2023	Andrea Hahmann, DTU Wind	Proofreading and peer review
1.1	11.12.2023	Thomas Schauppenlehner, BOKU Vienna	Proofreading and peer review
1.2	13.12.2023	Ruihong Chen, ETH Zurich	Consolidation of input from reviewers
COORDINATOR APPROVAL			
3.0	18.12.2023	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Coordinator review
3.1	18.12.2023	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Consolidation of input from coordinator
3.2	18.12.2023	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Coordinator approval
FINAL VERSION			
4.0	22.12.2023	S. Arapoglou (VUB)	Format review, version ready for submission

SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This report describes Deliverable 2.5 of the WIMBY project, a dataset on landscape impact metrics. The report introduces available national landscape scenic value datasets in Europe and describes the calculation steps of four produced measurable geospatial landscape metrics: naturalness, human impact, remoteness, and ruggedness. These delivered datasets have limitations on the used weights and simplified routes. Improvements and upscaling will be carried out in D2.6.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
CH	Switzerland
CLC	Corine land cover
DE	Germany
DEM	Digital elevation model
ECHOES	Energy CHOices supporting the Energy union and the Set-plan
GB	Great Britain
GIS	Geographic Information System
OSM	OpenStreetMap
WSL	Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable (D2.5) describes the first version of the landscape impact assessment from Task 2.3 (T2.3) that aims to estimate the landscape quality via different indicators derived from open data available at a European level. The overall objective is to uncover relationships between the perceived landscape scenic quality and measurable landscape metrics to derive a map of European landscape scenic value. The developed landscape datasets will serve as input for WP4 on system optimization and WP5 on interactive maps.

A literature review on existing landscape datasets and metrics was carried out, and useful findings are presented in Sections 2 and 3. Three datasets on national landscape scenicness were gathered and will be used for training or validation.

Using Switzerland as a case study, we obtained publicly available geospatial datasets and reproduced landscape metrics used in existing studies: naturalness, remoteness, human impact, and ruggedness. A preliminary pairwise correlation study was conducted between the Swiss national landscape quality survey data and derived landscape metrics. We found a Pearson correlation coefficient of around 0.2, indicating a very weak linear correlation.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

D2.5 is the first deliverable of T2.3 to develop a first version of different landscape metrics for a selected country/region (Switzerland) as a case study, which has been achieved according to plan. Another objective was to examine if correlations between crowd-sourced/survey data and landscape metrics exist. The results of the analysis on the Swiss case demonstrate very weak positive and negative correlations. Possible causes of the insignificant correlations and next steps are discussed in Section 4.

1. Overview

D2.5 develops landscape metrics maps based on open data that can be used to estimate the landscape scenic value at a European level. Section 2 introduces the existing crowd-sourced datasets and surveys on landscape scenic quality in three European countries together with their respective details. Section 3 describes the calculation of four main geospatial indicators reproduced following the Swiss landscape wilderness study [1] by replacing all Swiss-specific data sources with open-source European data. Other potential landscape metrics are introduced as well. Section 4 discusses the limitations and lists the next steps for Deliverable 2.6. The link to the produced landscape metrics is included in the Annex.

2. Existing landscape quality dataset

Landscape scenicness refers to the aesthetic value of the landscape perceived by humans. We gathered known national landscape scenicness datasets in Europe. There are three datasets that have been either applied to energy system modelling or mentioned in related landscape quality studies. They are the ScenicOrNot dataset for Great Britain (GB) [2], [3], the scenic landscape quality for Germany (DE) [4], and the landscape quality survey for Switzerland (CH) carried out by the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research (WSL) [5]. Details of the three datasets are presented in Sections 2.1 to 2.3.

2.1 ScenicOrNot (GB)

ScenicOrNot (<http://scenicornot.datasciencelab.co.uk/>) offers a platform for the collection of crowd-sourced scenic evaluations, operating at a spatial resolution of 1 km² throughout Great Britain. The platform presents users with randomly selected geotagged photographs, predominantly captured at eye level. Participants are asked to assign integer ratings on a scale from 1 to 10, with 10 denoting 'highly scenic' and 1 indicating 'not scenic at all.' The photographs are curated by Geograph (<http://www.geograph.org.uk>), a web-based initiative committed to collecting and referencing geographically representative imagery covering every square kilometer of the British Isles.

McKenna et. al [2] used the obtained data that contains the scenic values values for all photographs rated three times or more, covering around 95% of the 1 km squares of land mass in GB. The data is in both raster and shapefile format. The raster data is visualized in Figure 1.

2.2 Scenic landscape quality (DE)

The scenic landscape quality in Germany was estimated by Roth et al. [4] using GIS-based scenic quality modelling based on empirical data gathered from online visual landscape assessment surveys. The authors used 17 regressors calculated in the viewsheds in 1 km² resolution from all used photographs to determine the correlations based on 44,000 assessments. The data in raster format is shown in Figure 2.

2.3 Landscape quality survey (CH)

The WSL, a research institute in Switzerland focusing on forest, snow, and landscape conducted a representative national survey in 2021 on landscape quality covering different genders, age groups, and linguistic regions [5].

There were 2,000 responses where residents were asked to rate their home landscape. However, due to the low number of responses, the dataset does not cover all Swiss municipalities, resulting in a low spatial resolution overall and some gaps in the data, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1 – ScenicOrNot dataset for Great Britain rated from 1 (low) to 10 (high) in 1 km² resolution [2]

Figure 2 – Scenic landscape quality dataset for Germany rated from 1 (low) to 9 (high) in 1 km² resolution [4]

Figure 3 – Landscape quality for Switzerland rated from 1 (low) to 10 (high) on the municipality level (white color indicates no data) [5]

3. Existing landscape metrics

After gathering the available national landscape scenicness data, the next step was reproducing useful geospatial indicators as landscape metrics with only open data across Europe. There have been studies using GIS-based approaches to estimate landscape coherence [6] and wilderness [1]. These studies use indicators derived from various datasets such as land cover, landform, digital elevation model (DEM), forest inventory, and infrastructure from OpenStreetMap (OSM), etc. Land cover refers to the physical coverage of the Earth's surface [7], e.g., forests, grasslands, croplands, lakes, etc. The landform is a feature on the Earth's surface that is part of the terrain, such as mountains, hills, and plateaus [8].

The following sections (Sections 3.1 to 3.4) present the details of reproducing the four indicators from the wilderness study [1] for Switzerland using Europe-wide open data. Section 3.5 shows the correlation analysis between the Swiss survey data and the calculated indicators, while Section 3.6 discusses some more potential indicators for a later stage.

3.1 Naturalness

Naturalness is an indicator used to assess the extent of native flora and fauna in an area and the degree to which the current habitat reflects its original state [1]. It is quantified using a hemeroby scale, ranging from 1 to 5. A value of 1 signifies conditions close to a natural environment, while 5 indicates a highly modified environment. Following the expert survey by Radford et al. [1], each land cover class from Corine Land Cover (CLC) [7] was assigned a hemeroby index, as shown in Table 1. Different hemeroby indices were applied to shrubs and herbaceous vegetation above and below the treeline, distinguishing alpine and subalpine regions (hemeroby index 4) from those at lower elevations (hemeroby index 2). The elevation data comes from the Copernicus digital elevation model (DEM) [9].

Table 1 – Corine land cover classes with their assigned hemeroby indices from [1]

Class	Hemeroby Index
Continuous urban fabric	5
Discontinuous urban fabric	5
Industrial or commercial units	5
Road and rail networks and associated land	5
Port areas	5
Airports	5
Mineral extraction sites	5

Class	Hemeroby Index
Dump sites	5
Construction sites	5
Vineyards	5
Sport and leisure facilities	5
Non-irrigated arable land	4
Green urban areas	4
Permanently irrigated land	4
Rice fields	4
Olive groves	4
Annual crops associated with permanent crops	4
Complex cultivation patterns	4
Agro-forestry areas	4
Fruit trees and berry plantations	3
Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation	3
Pastures	2
Broad-leaved forest (Altitude dependent)	2 or 4
Coniferous forest (Altitude dependent)	2 or 4
Mixed forest (Altitude dependent)	2 or 4
Natural grassland (Altitude dependent)	2 or 4
Moors and heathland (Altitude dependent)	2 or 4
Sclerophyllous vegetation (Altitude dependent)	2 or 4
Transitional woodland/shrub (Altitude dependent)	2 or 4
Beaches, dunes, sands	1
Bare rock	1
Sparsely vegetated areas	1
Burnt areas	1
Glaciers and perpetual snow	1
Inland marshes	1
Peatbogs	1
Salt marshes	1
Salines	1
Intertidal flats	1
Water courses	1
Water bodies	1
Coastal lagoons	1
Estuaries	1
Sea and ocean	1

The result of the hemeroby classification is in raster format and has the same resolution as CLC [7], which is 100 m x 100 m. Figure 4 illustrates the obtained results for the case of Switzerland, where high naturalness

(hemeroby index of 1) corresponds to the mountainous regions and low naturalness (hemeroby index of 5) coincides with urban settlements. Major settlements tend to be sited next to large lakes (white areas) in the Swiss case.

Figure 4 – Naturalness map for Switzerland in 100 m x 100 m resolution based on CLC [7] and DEM [9] (1: high, 5: low); white areas are lakes excluded in the calculation

3.2 Human impact

Human impact refers to the influence of human activities on the landscape, encompassing both the physical structures created by humans and the traces they leave behind [1]. It considers mainly mobility, buildings, as well as miscellaneous infrastructure.

Regarding mobility, infrastructure such as roads, railways, airports, and even ski routes are considered. They have varying degrees of interference with the natural environment, including noise, light pollution, and modification of the original landscape.

Buildings consider residential, commercial, and industrial buildings, alpine huts, agriculture buildings, and bunkers. Each type of building has its own unique impact on the landscape, depending on the size and geometry.

Miscellaneous infrastructure incorporate additional infrastructure that do not fall under the two categories above yet still have a considerable

impact on the landscape. It includes transmission lines, farmland, camp sites, and others. The detailed categories are shown in Table 2.

To calculate the human impact score of each of the subcategories, an expert survey was carried out by Radford et al. [1] to gather the importance ratings (IR) of each subcategory. These IRs were used but reassigned to new subcategories in layers from CLC [7] and OSM [10] according to definitions. The weights were calculated as the IR divided by the sum of all IRs times the number of input data layers, as shown in Equation 1.

$$W_i = \frac{IR_i}{\sum_1^n IR_j} \times n \tag{1}$$

Where:

- W_i Weight of subcategory i
- IR_i Importance rating of subcategory i
- n Number of subcategories

The IRs and weights for each subcategory are presented in Table 2. A weighted linear combination of the area of each subcategory in each pixel is calculated as the human impact score, according to Equation 2.

$$HI = \frac{\sum_1^n W_i \times A_i}{A_{pixel}} \tag{2}$$

Where:

- HI Human impact score
- A_i Area of subcategory i
- A_{pixel} Area of one pixel

Table 2 – Human impact indicators with their importance ratings [1] and weights

Categories	Source	Importance Rating (IR)	Weight
Mobility:			
Mountain Stations	OSM	6	1.00
Airports	OSM	9	1.50
Motorways	OSM	9	1.50
Railways	OSM	9	1.50
Tracks	OSM	3.5	0.58
Hiking Routes / Trails	OSM	3.5	0.58
Skiing Routes	OSM	3.5	0.58
Highways	OSM	3.5	0.58
Buildings:			
Agricultural Buildings	OSM	6	1.00
Bunker	OSM	3.5	0.58

Categories	Source	Importance Rating (IR)	Weight
Castle	OSM	7	1.16
Ruins	OSM	5	0.83
Alpine Huts	OSM	5	0.83
Residential, Commercial and Industrial Buildings	CLC	9	1.50
Artificial vegetated surfaces	CLC	3.5	0.58
Power Plants	OSM	9	1.50
<u>Various:</u>			
Hunting Stands	OSM	3.5	0.58
Farmland	CLC	6	1.00
Forest	CLC	5	0.83
Glaciers	CLC	3.5	0.58
Camp Sites	OSM	7	1.16
Water Dams	OSM	9	1.50
Transmission Lines	OSM	9	1.50
Climbing Sites	OSM	3.5	0.58
Quarry	OSM	9	1.50

The resulting human impact scores were normalized to a scale of 1 to 5 (1: low, 5: high). Values smaller than 1 were rounded up to 1. Results are in raster format with a spatial resolution of 100 m x 100 m, as presented in Figure 5. It captures the alpine region as having low human impact, similar to high naturalness, but shows a clearer distinction between wild mountain ranges and infrastructure in mountains such as agricultural land, transmission lines, and skiing resorts.

Figure 5 – Human impact map for Switzerland in 100 m x 100 m resolution based on CLC [7] and OSM [10] (1: low, 5: high); white areas are lakes excluded in the calculation

3.3 Remoteness

Remoteness quantifies how accessible an area is. The isolation can provide refuges and habitats for wild species and offers individuals an opportunity to find consolation and experience tranquillity. Remoteness was calculated as the required walking time to the nearest civil point [1]. Civil points consist of a cluster of more than 10 buildings, public transportation stops, parking spaces, and cable car stations.

The travel time between pixels was determined by factors such as walking speed, distance, slope angle, and terrain. The expected movement speed over different land cover types and required travel time per 100 m for different slope angles are shown in Table 3. Slope angles can be calculated from the altitudes at neighboring pixels provided by the DEM [9]. The total required travel time between two points can be calculated as the summation of the travel time between every neighboring pixels along the straight line connecting the two, as shown in Equation 3.

$$T = \sum_1^k t_i \quad 3$$

Where:

T Total required travel time

- t_i Travel time between pixel i and $i - 1$
- k Number of pixels crossed

Table 3 – Speed of movement over different land cover types, with their associated walking time in seconds for 100 m on different slope angles [1]

Land cover type	Speed (km/h)	Walking time (s) for 100 m on different slope angles				
		0-4°	4-8°	8-12°	12-16°	>16°
Paths/trails	4	86	128	170	210	247
Agriculture land	3.5	102	154	204	251	297
Forest	3	120	180	238	293	346
Dense, scrubby vegetation	2	181	269	356	440	519
Water	Barrier	n/a				

To ensure a realistic estimation of remoteness for points near the Swiss border, the analysis considered points located outside the country's borders as well (within 500 m). The resulting travel time was categorized into scale of 1 to 5 as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 – Remoteness scale and the associated travel time

Remoteness	Accessibility in walking minutes
1	0 – 60
2	60 – 120
3	120 – 300
4	300 – 600
5	> 600

The result for Switzerland is in raster with a spatial resolution of 100 m x 100 m, as shown in Figure 6. Due to the good coverage of the Swiss transport networks and infrastructure, only several mountain peaks achieve a remoteness rating of 5, while most of the alpine regions still can be accessed within 600 minutes from the closest civil point. The accessible areas (remoteness = 1) in the alpine region follow the valleys where major towns with train stations and bus stops are located. The Swiss central plateau (“Mittelland” in German) is highly accessible with a remoteness rating of 1.

Figure 6 – Remoteness map for Switzerland in 100 m x 100 m resolution based on DEM [9], CLC[7], and OSM [10] (1: low, 5: high); white areas are lakes excluded in the calculation

3.4 Ruggedness

Ruggedness describes the topology of the terrain in terms of how uneven the landscape appears. Especially in mountainous regions, ruggedness plays an important role in describing the terrain. The input data was the EU-DEM from Copernicus [9] collected by Ryberg et al. [11], which has a resolution of 25 m x 25 m. The ruggedness was calculated as the standard deviation (SD) of the elevation of the terrain within a 250 m radius. For each pixel, a circular neighborhood with a 250 m radius was defined and the SD of all pixels within the neighborhood was calculated according to Equation 4 below.

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum |x - \mu|^2}{N}} \quad 4$$

Where:

- x Elevation of raster value
- μ Mean value of raster values within circular neighbourhood
- N Number of raster values within circular neighbourhood

Similar to the human impact, the calculated ruggedness was normalized to the scale of 1 to 5 (1: low, 5: high). Figure 7 shows the obtained

results for Switzerland as raster with a spatial resolution of 100 m x 100 m, as shown in. High ruggedness only appears in the alpine region without covering the majority of the area. The northern part of Switzerland (Mittelland) is mostly flat with only small variations.

Figure 7 – Ruggedness map for Switzerland in 100 m x 100 m resolution based on DEM [9] (1: low, 5: high); where all lake surfaces are rated as ruggedness 1

3.5 Correlation analysis

After calculating the four indicators, a correlation analysis was performed between the Swiss scenicness survey dataset [5] and the calculated indicators. Since the survey data recorded 874 municipalities, all the responses from the same municipality were averaged. The same applied to the four calculated indicators. We used a Pearson correlation coefficient to test for a linear correlation between the scenicness and four indicators. The coefficient ranges from -1 to 1, where an absolute value of 1 implies a perfect linear relationship between the two variables, and an absolute value of 0 indicates no relationship [12]. The results are shown in Table 5, where none of the coefficients has an absolute value higher than 0.3, indicating very weak positive and weak negative correlations.

Table 5 – Pearson correlation coefficients between scenicness and four indicators

Calculated Indicators	Pearson correlation coefficient with scenicness
Naturalness	-0.24
Human Impact	-0.21
Remoteness	0.14
Ruggedness	0.15

For a visual inspection of the possible non-linear correlations, the scatterplots of scenicness against four indicators are shown in Figure 8. No evident non-linear correlations can be seen from the figures. Possible causes of the low correlations will be discussed in Section 4.

Figure 8 – Mean scenicness values against mean values of naturalness, human impact, remoteness, and ruggedness in each reported Swiss municipality

3.6 Other potential indicators

Besides the four employed indicators (naturalness, human impact, remoteness, ruggedness) above from the landscape wilderness study, there are still other potential indicators to explore. The landscape coherence proposed by Karasov et al. [6] combines both landcovers and landforms, which is shown to be positively correlated with most photographed regions on social media. However, this indicator is hard to upscale due to the lack of open landform data on a European scale. Another useful landscape metric

by Fragstats software [13] is the composition of a map, which includes the proportional abundance of each class, richness (number of different patch types), evenness (relative abundance of different patch types), and diversity (a composite measure of richness and evenness). Detailed calculations of these new metrics are yet to be investigated.

4. Discussion and next steps

There are limitations to the four calculated indicators. Naturalness and human impact overlap in definition, despite different focuses (one on land cover, the other on infrastructure). Although the wilderness study by Radford et al. [1] reveals a high independence of the two indicators, the resulting maps present a high level of similarity. Human impact is a weighted linear combination of importance ratings from a landscape expert survey. The importance rating can be subjective, and whether these ratings can be applied to other countries with cultural differences is still uncertain. As for remoteness, the travel time calculation assumes a straight line and does not consider walking on designated paths, which can lead to an overall underestimation of the travel time. Additionally, unclimbable steep slopes are not differentiated from slopes higher than 16°, making many mountain peaks and cliffs seem more reachable than they actually are.

It should be noted that water bodies are always excluded from these indicators. Although floating wind turbines on lakes are not taken into account in this research project, lakeside areas always tend to be considered as highly scenic, especially in the Swiss case. Therefore, proximity to water bodies and/or abundance of water within a region should also be investigated.

In the correlation analysis, the low coefficients found could result from the low spatial resolution of the survey data. In each municipality, there can be various types of landscapes. However, the lack of geotags in the survey responses restricted the spatial details. The averaging of each municipality smoothed out the landscape variation within the region, leading to the loss of accuracy. A higher spatial resolution of the landscape scenicness data can potentially provide much better results.

The ScenicOrNot dataset [2] is geotagged with locations where the photograph is taken; therefore, the scenic rating is not for the tagged location, but the viewshed of it. Large-scale viewshed analysis would need to be carried out for each location of the photograph. The considered GIS landscape metrics will be investigated in each viewshed instead of pixels in the next steps of the analysis.

To quantify the landscape impact of wind turbines on residents, a combination of landscape scenic quality, visibility to populations, and local acceptance towards renewables (especially wind) should be considered. Therefore, with the proposed/optimized wind turbine locations given by T2.1,

another viewshed analysis should be conducted to determine how much population would be affected in the vicinity. Additionally, the level of the impact will vary depending on the local acceptance of renewables. A dataset from international surveys by Energy CHOices supporting the Energy Union and the Set-plan (ECHOES) [14] on public acceptance towards renewable energy can be useful at a later stage.

The next steps for D2.6 next year are as follows:

- Produce additional potential landscape metrics/indicators;
- Improve the four indicators if possible;
- Automate and carry out large-scale viewshed analysis on the supercomputer;
- Regression study on the ScenicOrNot dataset and all derived indicators;
- Upscale the calculation to Europe to obtain the scenicness map;
- Viewshed analysis on proposed wind turbine locations and determine the urban areas that are affected;
- Combine the public acceptance data to quantify the landscape impact on residents.

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ANNEX

For WIMBY reviewers: (Yoda)

Research/research-wimby-

data/wimby_intermediate_results/D2.5_landscape_impact_metrics

